

FEATURES OF THE FORMATION AND MANIFESTATION OF TOLERANT BEHAVIOR IN HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

Narshabayeva Aliya Yumutbaevna,

University of Innovation Technologies, Associate Professor of the Department of Philology PhD
narshabina1970@gmail.com

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Abstract. The article examines the features of the formation and manifestation of tolerant behavior among university students. Tolerance is considered as an integrative personal quality that includes cognitive, emotional-value and behavioral components. The study analyzes psychological and pedagogical factors influencing the development of tolerant behavior in the university educational environment. Special attention is paid to pedagogical means that contribute to the formation of tolerance in the process of educational interaction.

Keywords: tolerance, tolerant behavior, students, higher education, educational environment.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются особенности формирования и проявления толерантного поведения у студентов высших учебных заведений. Толерантность рассматривается как интегративное личностное качество, включающее когнитивный, эмоционально-ценностный и поведенческий компоненты. В исследовании анализируются психолого-педагогические факторы, влияющие на развитие толерантного поведения в образовательной среде вуза. Особое внимание уделяется педагогическим средствам, способствующим формированию толерантности в процессе образовательного взаимодействия.

Ключевые слова: толерантность, толерантное поведение, студенты, высшее образование, образовательная среда.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabarlari orasida tolerant xulq-atvorning shakllanishi va namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tolerantlik kognitiv, emotsional-qadriyatli hamda xulq-atvor komponentlarini o'z ichiga oluvchi integrativ shaxsiy sifat sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda oliy ta'lim muhitida tolerant xulq-atvorning rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi psixologik va pedagogik omillar tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, ta'limiy o'zaro hamkorlik jarayonida tolerantlikni shakllantirishga xizmat qiluvchi pedagogik vositalarga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tolerantlik, tolerant xulq-atvor, talabalar, oliy ta'lim, ta'lim muhiti.

Introduction. In the context of globalization, academic mobility, and the intensification of intercultural contacts, the problem of forming tolerant behavior in students is acquiring special social and pedagogical significance. The modern higher education institution serves as a space for active interaction between representatives of various cultures, social groups, and worldview positions, which requires students to have a high level of communicative culture and the ability for constructive dialogue.

Tolerance in the student environment is considered a crucial personal quality that ensures successful socialization, conflict prevention, and the formation of civic responsibility. In this regard, the task of scientifically analyzing the features of the formation and manifestation of tolerant behavior in higher education students, as well as identifying pedagogical means contributing to its development, is becoming relevant.

Tolerance as a socio-psychological characteristic of the individual in the educational environment is considered as the ability to respect the diversity of cultures, views, and social groups, as well as to constructive interaction in interpersonal situations [1;]. The formation of tolerance is one of the key tasks of modern higher education, as the development of this competence contributes to the social adaptation of students in a multinational and multicultural space [5;].

However, conceptual approaches to the study of tolerance are diverse: from tolerance as a personal attitude and social skill to a pedagogical strategy for fostering civic position and intercultural competence of students [3;].

Essay on the formation of students' tolerance in a multicultural environment of the university. This indicates the need for a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon of tolerance in the context of higher education.

Literary review. The problem of forming tolerant behavior of the individual occupies an important place in modern psychological and pedagogical research, which is due to social changes, the strengthening of intercultural contacts, and the increasing role of education in the formation of value attitudes of young people. In scientific literature, tolerance is considered as a complex integrative quality of personality, including cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components.

In a number of studies, tolerance is defined as a person's ability to accept and respect social, cultural, and ideological diversity, as well as readiness for constructive interaction in the face of differences. From the perspective of the cultural-historical approach, tolerance is viewed as a result of the socialization of the individual and the assimilation of socially significant norms and values in the process of activity and communication. [2;].

Pedagogical research emphasizes the leading role of the educational environment in the formation of students' tolerant behavior. According to V. A. Slastenin, the educational potential of the educational process is realized through the organization of joint activities, dialogue, and the inclusion of students in socially significant forms of interaction [9;]. In this context, the university is considered as a space for the purposeful formation of value orientations and models of social behavior of students.

A significant contribution to the study of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of tolerance was made by research devoted to the competency-based approach. A. V. Khutorskoy considers tolerance as an important component of a person's social and communicative competence, formed in the process of active educational interaction [10;]. This approach allows us to consider tolerant behavior not only as a value orientation but also as a practical ability for social interaction.

In scientific literature, special attention is paid to the role of interactive and dialogic teaching methods in the formation of tolerance. E. S. Pulat emphasizes that active forms of

educational activity create conditions for the development of cooperation skills, mutual understanding, and respect for a different position, which is especially significant in student environments [7;].

The socio-cultural aspect of the problem is presented in the works of V. V. Safonova, who considers tolerance as the result of introducing students to the values of cultural dialogue and understanding the cultural diversity of modern society [8;]. This approach emphasizes the need to include students in a situation of intercultural interaction as a condition for the formation of stable tolerant attitudes.

Analysis of scientific sources shows that, despite a significant number of studies devoted to the problem of tolerance, the issues of the peculiarities of the formation and manifestation of tolerant behavior specifically in the student environment remain insufficiently systematized. Existing works, as a rule, emphasize either the value-normative understanding of tolerance or individual pedagogical means of its formation, without a holistic consideration of the component structure and the conditions for its manifestation in the educational environment of the university. At the same time, the relationship between the cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components of tolerance and the pedagogical means of their formation in the process of educational interaction remains insufficiently studied. This determined the scientific novelty of this research, which consists in a comprehensive analysis of the features of the formation and manifestation of tolerant behavior of university students in the context of purposeful pedagogical organization of the educational environment.

Methods. The methodological basis of the research was the personality-oriented, competency-based, and sociocultural approaches, which allow us to consider tolerance as an integrative personal education and the result of purposeful pedagogical influence on the educational environment of the university. The student-centered approach ensured consideration of students' individual characteristics, their value orientations, and interpersonal interaction experiences. The competency-based approach made it possible to consider tolerant behavior as an important component of the social and communicative competence of the future specialist. The sociocultural approach provided an analysis of tolerance in the context of cultural diversity and social interaction in the student environment.

The research used a complex of complementary theoretical and empirical methods that ensure the integrity and reliability of the obtained results. Theoretical methods included the analysis and generalization of psychological-pedagogical, sociological, and philosophical literature on the problem of tolerance, which made it possible to clarify the conceptual apparatus of the study, determine the structure of tolerant behavior, and identify the main scientific approaches to its formation in higher education.

Empirical methods included pedagogical observation of students' academic and extracurricular activities, aimed at recording the real manifestations of tolerant and intolerant behavior in the process of interpersonal and group interaction. Observation was carried out during classroom sessions, group work, discussions, and joint activities of students, which made it possible to identify the features of communicative behavior and the nature of interpersonal relationships in the student environment.

Additionally, an analysis of educational and communicative interaction situations was applied, which allows for the identification of typical behavioral models of students in the context of cooperation, dialogue, and conflict resolution. This method ensured the identification of the specifics of manifestations of the cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components of tolerance.

For the scientific understanding and generalization of the obtained empirical data, the interpretive method was used, aimed at correlating the research results with the theoretical provisions of pedagogy and educational psychology, as well as identifying the patterns of tolerant behavior formation in the student environment [5;].

The use of the combination of these methods ensured the systematic and comprehensive nature of the research and allowed for obtaining substantiated conclusions about the peculiarities of the formation and manifestation of tolerant behavior in university students.

Results. The research results showed that students' tolerant behavior has a multi-level and component character and manifests itself in the cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral spheres of personality. Analysis of pedagogical observation data and learning situations of interaction indicates that these components are interconnected and form unevenly, depending on the conditions of the educational environment and the nature of learning activities.

It has been established that the cognitive component of tolerance is expressed in students' awareness of the value of cultural, social, and worldview diversity, knowledge of the norms of interpersonal and intercultural interaction, and understanding the significance of respectful attitude towards a different position. Students with a formed cognitive component demonstrated a more conscious attitude towards differences and greater readiness for dialogue, which was manifested in the argumentation of statements and the desire to understand the interlocutor's position.

The emotional-value component of tolerance manifested itself in the ability to empathize, accept another person, and have a positive emotional attitude towards differences. During observations of group and project work, it was noted that students' emotional involvement and experience of a collaborative situation contribute to reducing tension in communication and forming trusting relationships. This component was closely

related to the nature of educational interaction and the availability of conditions for open expression of opinions and feelings.

The behavioral component of tolerance was reflected in specific forms of educational and interpersonal interaction: the ability to conduct a constructive dialogue, cooperate in the group, consider the partner's position, and resolve communicative difficulties in non-violent ways.

Students with a higher level of formation of this component demonstrated readiness for joint decision-making, adherence to communication rules, and respectful attitude towards different viewpoints in the learning process.

Based on the analysis of pedagogical practice, pedagogical tools most effectively influencing the formation of students' tolerant behavior were identified. These include interactive forms of learning, group and project activities, discussion methods, and the analysis of problematic communicative situations. The use of these tools creates conditions for the active involvement of students in the educational process and contributes to the transition of tolerance from the level of conscious attitudes to the level of stable behavioral manifestations.

Overall, the obtained results confirm that the formation of students' tolerant behavior in university conditions is a dynamic process dependent on the purposeful pedagogical organization of the educational environment and the nature of educational interaction.

Discussion. The interpretation of the obtained results allows us to consider students' tolerant behavior as a dynamic personality formation, formed in the process of purposeful educational interaction. The component structure of tolerance identified during the study confirms its multifaceted nature and the need for a comprehensive pedagogical influence, oriented simultaneously towards the cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral spheres of the individual.

The results regarding the cognitive component of tolerance indicate that the conscious acceptance of cultural and social differences is formed primarily in the context of problem-based and dialogic learning. Knowing the norms of interpersonal interaction and understanding the value of diversity acts as a necessary, but insufficient condition for the manifestation of tolerant behavior, which confirms the conclusion about the need to reinforce them with practical experience of interaction. This conclusion aligns with the provisions of pedagogical theory regarding the leading role of students' activity in the process of assimilating social norms and values. [5;].

Analysis of the emotional-value component of tolerance allows us to assert that the development of empathy and acceptance of another person largely depends on the nature of the educational environment and the emotional climate of educational interaction. Joint activity, group work, and discussion of problematic situations create conditions for the

formation of a positive emotional experience of communication, contributing to the reduction of tension and the overcoming of stereotypical attitudes. This confirms the thesis that tolerance cannot be formed solely at the level of rational knowledge, but requires emotional experience and personal meaning. [11;]

The behavioral component of tolerance, manifested in specific forms of interaction, is most clearly formed in the context of active and interactive teaching methods. The ability to conduct a dialogue, cooperate, and constructively resolve communicative difficulties is the result of systematically involving students in a situation of joint decision-making and responsibility for the result of collective activity. The obtained data confirm the effectiveness of pedagogical tools focused on the practice of social interaction, which aligns with the conclusions of modern research in higher education [7;].

Thus, the discussion of the research results allows us to conclude that the formation of students' tolerant behavior requires a holistic pedagogical approach that assumes a coordinated influence on all components of tolerance. The purposeful organization of the university's educational environment and the use of active forms of learning ensure the transition of tolerance from the level of declared attitudes to the level of stable personal and behavioral manifestations.

Thus, the analysis and interpretation of the obtained results allow us to consider the tolerant behavior of university students as a result of targeted and systematic pedagogical influence. The formation of tolerance is not spontaneous, but requires the creation of specially organized conditions for educational interaction, ensuring the harmonious development of cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components. The patterns identified during the research confirm the necessity of integrating pedagogical tools focused on dialogue, cooperation, and practical experience of interpersonal interaction, which creates a theoretical and empirical basis for the generalizing conclusions presented in the conclusion.

Conclusion. The conducted research allows us to conclude that the formation of tolerant behavior in university students is a purposeful and systematic pedagogical process implemented in a specially organized educational environment. Tolerance manifests as an integrative personal education that includes cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components, the development of which requires coordinated pedagogical influence.

It has been established that the most effective formation of tolerant behavior is ensured when using active and interactive forms of educational activity oriented towards dialogue, cooperation, and practical experience of interpersonal interaction. It is precisely such conditions that contribute to the transition of tolerance from the level of conscious value attitudes to the level of stable behavioral manifestations in the student environment.

The obtained results can be used in the practice of higher education in designing educational programs, organizing the educational process, and developing methodological

recommendations aimed at forming students' tolerance, communicative culture, and social responsibility. The prospects for further research are related to refining the diagnostic tools for assessing tolerant behavior and experimentally verifying the effectiveness of individual pedagogical tools.

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